

Assessing the Economic Resilience of United India Insurance Company Limited: A Comparative Analysis of Pre-Covid and Post-Covid Periods

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Abstract: This study conducts a comprehensive financial analysis of United India Insurance Company Limited, examining its performance before and after the onset of the Covid-19 pandemic. By utilizing financial data spanning both periods, various metrics such as liquidity, profitability, solvency, and efficiency are evaluated to discern the impact of the pandemic on the company's financial health and operational dynamics. Through the application of financial ratios, trends, and comparative analysis techniques, this research aims to provide insights into the resilience and adaptability of United India Insurance Company Limited amidst the unprecedented challenges brought forth by the pandemic. The findings of this study are expected to contribute to a deeper understanding of the insurance sector's response to external crises and inform stakeholders, policymakers, and industry practitioners about potential strategies for navigating future uncertainties.

Index Terms : financial health, Comparative analysis, financial indicators, Covid-19 pandemic, economic resilience

I. INTRODUCTION

The financial landscape of companies across various industries has been significantly influenced by the Covid-19 pandemic, presenting both challenges and opportunities for analysis and adaptation. In this context, this study embarks on a comprehensive examination of the performance of United India Insurance Company Limited, a prominent player in the insurance sector, before and after the advent of the pandemic. By delving into the financial data encompassing these distinct periods, this research endeavors to shed light on the effects of the pandemic on the company's financial health and operational dynamics. Through the lens of various critical metrics such as liquidity, profitability, solvency, and efficiency, this study aims to unravel the multifaceted impacts of the pandemic on United India Insurance Company Limited. Leveraging financial ratios, trend analysis, and comparative techniques, the research endeavors to provide a nuanced understanding of how the company navigated through the challenges posed by the pandemic, assessing its resilience and adaptability in the face of unprecedented disruptions. Furthermore, this study aspires to contribute valuable insights to the broader understanding of the insurance sector's response to external crises, highlighting the strategies adopted by United India Insurance Company Limited to mitigate risks and sustain its operations. By informing stakeholders, policymakers, and industry practitioners, this research seeks to facilitate informed decision-making and chart potential pathways for navigating future uncertainties in the ever-evolving business landscape.

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Review of literature is essential since it familiarizes the researcher with concepts and conclusions already evolved by earlier analysis. It also enables the here, researcher to find out the scope of study and frame suitable objectives for the proposed evaluation. Since the proposal of the study is to measure the comparative selected Sectoral mutual funds in India. It also includes the opinions expressed by various authors in leading articles, journals and books.

1. Choi 2013 and Tamegawa 2016 This study highlights that due to a severe liquidity freeze, many financial institutions had failed and their failures created more uncertainty about the future for financial market and economic recovery. Information asymmetry during the financial crisis could also influence economic stability of a nation, triggered by conflict of interests between the financial service providers and the regulatory body.
2. Liargovas and Skandalis 2008 and Omondi and Muturi 2013 Despite the various definitions, interpretations and measurements of financial performance, there is no ultimate consensus on the best way to measure performance and to identify the factors that affect financial performance.
3. Haiss & Sümegi, 2008, Malik 2011 It contributes to economic growth, efficient resource allocation, reduction of transaction costs, creation of liquidity, facilitation of the economies of scale in investment, and the spread of financial losses.
4. Schich (2009) he argues that during the crises, insurers experience face valuation pressure which is caused by assets that are mostly held in bonds and stocks. This study seeks to highlight the effect of the financial crisis as shown in the rating grades' changes by utilising comparative analyses.
5. Kripa & Ajasllari (2016) Researcher has taken under study the impact of growth rate, liabilities, liquidity, fixed assets, volume of capital and company size on the profitability of insurance companies.

3. Research Objectives

Main objectives of this Paper are as follows

- To study the financial performance of United Insurance Company Limited.
- To analyses and compare the profitability, solvency, liquidity performance of United Insurance Company Limited Pre-Covid and Post-Covid Periods.

4. Research Hypotheses

For analyzing the objectives of the study, the following null hypothesis is to be tested:

- H01: There is no difference of profitability performance of United Insurance Company Limited Before and After the Covid-19 Era.
- H02: There is no difference of liquidity performance of United Insurance Company Limited Pre- Before and After the Covid-19 Era.
- H03: There is no difference of solvency performance of United Insurance Company Limited Before and After the Covid-19 Era..
- * H04: There is no difference of operating performance of United Insurance Company Limited Before and After the Covid-19 Era.

5. Methodology

The design of the present study is an analytical in nature and covers the top performed 10 Sectoral mutual funds for period of 10 years from 2013 to 2023. The data which is required for the analysis and that could fulfil our objectives has been collected mainly from two sources, viz 1) primary and 2) secondary data.

Primary data is collected from the concerned official of each sector of selected mutual funds and mutual funds experts through interviews and discussions regarding different aspects of the mutual funds.

The study is also based on the secondary data obtained from the Reports of Association of mutual funds and Money control in India. Besides, the facts, figures and findings advanced in similar earlier studies and the SEBI Reports are also used to supplement the secondary data.

For assessing the behavior of data statistical techniques have been used such as statistical descriptions, correlation analysis and t-test is used for this study. For these statistical measures are calculated by using SPSS software.

6. Tools Used for Study Analysis

Accounting ratios, risk analysis, portfolio analysis and Statistical tools are used for analysis:

1. Accounting ratios: Net Assets ratio, cash ratio, Equity ratio, Expenses ratio, Information ratio, NAV, YTD, Sortine ratio and CAGR.
2. Risk Analysis: Systematic risk, Unsystematic risk, Standard deviation and Beta.
3. Portfolio Performance Analysis: Sharpe performance Index, Treynor performance Index and Jensen performance Index.
4. Statistical Analysis: Percentages, least square trend, correlation and t-test.

7. Scope and Limitation of Study:

The below mentioned are the constraints under which, studies are carried out

- a. The collection of data analysis is restricted to Reports of Association of mutual funds and Money control in India only.
- b. The study is limited by time constraints.
- c. The study is based mainly on secondary data collected from websites of NSE, BSE and Reports of Association of mutual funds and Money control in India.

8. Analysis of the Study:

Pre and Post Covid analysis of Profitability Performance:

i) Net Profit Ratio:

$$\text{Net Profit Ratio} = \frac{\text{Net Profit}}{\text{Total Income}} \times 100$$

Table 4.1: Net Profit Ratio analysis

Pre-Covid				Post-Covid			
FY	PAT (in Cr)	Total Income (in Cr)	Ratio (%)	FY	PAT (in Cr)	Total Income (in Cr)	Ratio (%)
2016-17	-1913.53	15455.98	-12.38	2019-20	-1485.85	16534.95	-8.99
2017-18	1002.66	15475.24	6.48	2020-21	-984.68	16244.90	-6.06
2018-19	-1877.91	16678.77	-11.26	2022-23	-2135.55	17009.50	-12.56
Total	-2788.78	47609.99		Total	-4606.08	49789.35	
Average	-929.59	15870.00	-5.86	Average	-1535.36	16596.45	-9.25

Fig 4.1: Bar Chart that shows Net Profit Ratio data of UIICL for past 6 years

Source: Annual reports of UIICL taken from uiic.co.in/public-disclosure

Interpretation:

It can be seen from the table 4.1 and figure 4.1 representing the profitability performance of UIICL before and after covid are as follows: During pre-covid, the average net profit ratio from FY 2016-17 to 2018-19 was -5.86% whereas the average net profit ratio from FY 2019-20 to 2022-23 was -9.25%.

It indicates that UIIC post-covid net profit has been decreased from -5.86% to -9.25%.

ii) *Operating Profit Ratio:*

Pre-Covid				Post-Covid			
FY	Operating Profit (in Cr)	Total Income (in Cr)	Ratio (%)	FY	Operating Profit (in Cr)	Total Income (in Cr)	Ratio (%)
2016-17	-2335.08	15455.98	-15.11	2019-20	-1603.54	16534.95	-9.70
2017-18	542.55	15475.24	3.51	2020-21	-1053.29	16244.90	-6.48
2018-19	-2137.38	16678.77	-12.81	2022-23	-1677.88	17009.50	-9.86
Total	-3929.91	47609.99		Total	-4334.71	49789.35	
Average	-1309.97	158670.00	-8.25	Average	-1444.90	16596.45	-8.71

$$\text{Operating Profit Ratio} = \frac{\text{Operating Profit}}{\text{Total Income}} \times 100$$

Fig 4.2: Bar Chart that shows Operating Profit Ratio data of UIICL for past 6 years

Source: Annual reports of UIICL taken from uiic.co.in/public-disclosures

Interpretation:

It can be observed from the table 4.2 and figure 4.2 representing the profitability performance of UIICL before and after covid are as stated as: The average operating profit ratio from FY 2016-17 to 2018-19 during pre-covid period was -8.25% whereas the post-covid average operating profit ratio from FY 2019-20 to 2022-23 was -8.71%. It specifies that UIIC's Operating profit has been decreased from -8.25% to -8.71% during its post-covid period.

Pre and Post Covid analysis of Liquidity Performance:**i) Current Ratio:**

Current Assets: Cash and Bank balances plus advances

Current Liabilities: Current Liabilities including provisions

$$\text{Current Ratio} = \frac{\text{Current Assets}}{\text{Current Liabilities}}$$

Table 4.3: Current Ratio analysis

Pre-Covid				Post-Covid			
FY	Current Assets (in Cr)	Current Liabilities (in Cr)	Ratio (times)	FY	Current Assets (in Cr)	Current Liabilities (in Cr)	Ratio (times)
2016-17	6282.47	24299.95	0.26	2019-20	7624.20	34214.62	0.26
2017-18	5919.92	26265.89	0.23	2020-21	9482.36	36100.58	0.22
2018-19	5663.88	30410.27	0.19	2022-23	8579.96	38904.83	0.24
Total	17866.27	80976.11		Total	25686.52	109220.03	
Average	5955.42	26992.04	0.22	Average	8562.17	36406.68	0.24

Fig 4.3: Bar Chart that shows Current Ratio data of UIICL for past 6 years

Source: Annual reports of UIICL taken from uiic.co.in/public-disclosures**Interpretation:**

It can be identified from the table 4.3 and figure 4.3 representing the liquidity performance of UIICL before and after covid are as: During pre-covid, the average current ratio from FY 2016-17 to 2018-19 was 0.22 times whereas the average current ratio from FY 2019-20 to 2022-23 was 0.24 times. It shows that current liquidity of UIICL has been increased from 0.22 to 0.24 times after Covid.

ii) Absolute Liquid Ratio:

$$\text{Absolute Liquid Ratio} = \frac{\text{Cash and Bank Balances}}{\text{Current Liabilities}}$$

Table 4.4: Absolute Liquid Ratio analysis

Pre-Covid				Post-Covid			
FY	Cash and Bank Bal. (in Cr)	Current Liabilities (in Cr)	Ratio (times)	FY	Cash and Bank Bal. (in Cr)	Current Liabilities (in Cr)	Ratio (times)
2016-17	1917.15	24299.95	0.08	2019-20	1735.66	34214.62	0.05
2017-18	2020.76	26265.89	0.08	2020-21	4092.11	36100.58	0.11
2018-19	1761.91	30410.27	0.06	2022-23	2668.05	38904.83	0.07
Total	5699.82	80976.11		Total	8495.82	109220.03	
Average	1899.94	26992.04	0.07	Average	2831.94	36406.68	0.08

Fig 4.4: Bar Chart that shows Absolute Liquid Ratio data of UIICL for past 6 years

Source: Annual reports of UIICL taken from uiic.co.in/public-disclosures

Interpretation:

It can be seen from the table 4.4 and figure 4.4 representing the liquidity performance of UIICL before and after covid are as :During pre-covid, the average Absolute Liquid ratio from FY 2016-17 to 2018-19 was 0.07 times whereas the average Absolute Liquid ratio from FY 2019-20 to 2022-23 was 0.08 times

It indicates that absolute liquidity of UIICL has been improved from 0.07 to 0.08 times after Covid.

Pre and Post Covid analysis of Solvency Performance:**i) Debt Equity Ratio:**

Debt: Borrowings+Minority interest + Deffered Tax Liability

Equity: Share capital + Revenue and Surplus

$$\text{Debt Equity Ratio} = \frac{\text{Debt}}{\text{Equity}}$$

Table 4.5: Debt Equity Ratio analysis

Pre-Covid				Post-Covid			
FY	Debt (in Cr)	Equity (in Cr)	Ratio (times)	FY	Debt (in Cr)	Equity (in Cr)	Ratio (times)
2016-17	4.99	4178.01	0.00	2019-20	922.21	3688.76	0.25
2017-18	908.02	5171.10	0.18	2020-21	939.53	4545.22	0.21
2018-19	908.45	2944.13	0.31	2022-23	900.00	4037.53	0.22
Total	1821.46	12293.24		Total	2761.74	12271.50	
Average	607.15	4097.75	0.15	Average	920.58	4090.50	0.23

Fig 4.5: Chart that shows Debt Equity Ratio data of UIICL for past 6 years

Source:

Annual reports of UIICL taken from uiic.co.in/public-disclosures

Interpretation: It can be identified from the table 4.5 and figure 4.5 representing the solvency performance of UIICL before and after covid are as stated that The average Debt Equity ratio from FY 2016-17 to 2018-19 was 0.15 times during pre-covid times whereas the average Debt Equity ratio from FY 2019-20 to 2022-23 was 0.23 times in post-covid period. There is no much Debt component in UIICL till FY 2016-17. It implies that Debt Equity ratio of UIICL has been increased from 0.15 to 0.23 times after Covid.

ii) Total Assets to Debt Ratio:

Total Assets : Investment (share holders’ + policy holders’) + loans + fixed assets and current assets

$$Total\ Assets\ to\ Debt\ Ratio = \frac{Total\ Assets}{Debt} \times 100$$

Table 4.6: Total Asset to Debt Ratio analysis

Pre-Covid				Post-Covid			
FY	Total Assets (Cr)	Debt (in Cr)	Ratio (%)	FY	Total Assets (Cr)	Debt (in Cr)	Ratio (%)
2016-17	34252.50	4.99	685749.37	2019-20	36468.01	922.21	3954.42
2017-18	36641.35	908.02	4035.32	2020-21	44412.16	939.53	4727.06
2018-19	38161.03	908.45	4200.68	2022-23	45066.38	900.00	5007.37
Total	109054.88	1821.46		Total	125946.55	2761.74	
Average	36351.63	607.15	5987.23	Average	41982.18	920.58	4560.41

Fig 4.6: Bar Chart that shows Total Assets to Debt ratio data of UIICL for past 6 years

Source: Annual reports of UIICL taken from uiic.co.in/public-disclosures

Interpretation:

It can be expressed from the table 4.6 and figure 4.6 representing the solvency performance of UIICL before and after covid are as follows:

During pre-covid, the average total assets to debt ratio from FY 2016-17 to 2018-19 was 5987% whereas the average total assets to debt ratio from FY 2019-20 to 2022-23 was 4560%. It indicates that Total assets to Debt ratio of UIICL has been reduced from 5987% to 4560% after Covid. This ratio is having it’s highest value in FY 2016-17.

Pre and Post Covid analysis of Operating Performance ratios:**Total Income to Fixed Assets Ratio:**

$$\text{Total Income to Fixed Assets Ratio} = \frac{\text{Total Income}}{\text{Fixed Assets}} \times 100$$

Table 4.8: Total Income to Fixed Assets Ratio

Pre-Covid				Post-Covid			
FY	Total Income (in Cr)	Fixed Assets (in Cr)	Ratio (%)	FY	Total Income (in Cr)	Fixed Assets (in Cr)	Ratio (%)
2016-17	15455.98	152.07	10163.68	2019-20	16534.95	271.99	6079.25
2017-18	15475.24	184.38	8393.13	2020-21	16244.90	258.08	6294.49
2018-19	16678.77	247.71	6733.08	2022-23	17009.50	449.89	3780.82
Total	47609.99	584.16		Total	49789.35	979.96	
Average	15870.00	194.72	8150.10	Average	16596.45	326.65	5080.75

Fig 4.8: Bar Chart that shows Total Income to Fixed Assets ratio data of UIICL for past 6 years

Source: Annual reports of UIICL taken from uiic.co.in/public-disclosures

Interpretation:

It can be seen from the table 4.8 and figure 4.8 representing the other performance of UIICL besides profitability, liquidity and solvency before and after covid are as follows:

During pre-covid, the average total income to fixed assets ratio from FY 2016-17 to 2018-19 was 8150% whereas the average total income to fixed assets ratio from FY 2019-20 to 2022-23 was 5081%. It shows that Total income to Fixed assets ratio of UIICL has been reduced from 8150% to 5081% after Covid.

ii) Total Income to Working Capital Ratio:

Working capital = Current Assets - Current Liabilities

$$\text{Total Income to Working Capital Ratio} = \frac{\text{Total Income}}{\text{Working Capital}}$$

Table 4.9: Total Income to Working Capital Ratio

Pre-Covid				Post-Covid			
FY	Total Income (in Cr)	Working Capital (in Cr)	Ratio (times)	FY	Total Income (in Cr)	Working Capital (in Cr)	Ratio (times)
2016-17	15455.98	-18017.47	-0.86	2019-20	16534.95	-26590.42	-0.62
2017-18	15475.24	-20345.97	-0.76	2020-21	16244.90	-26618.22	-0.61
2018-19	16678.77	-24746.39	-0.67	2022-23	17009.50	-30324.87	-0.56
Total	47609.99	-63109.84		Total	49789.35	-83533.51	
Average	15870.00	-21036.61	-0.75	Average	16596.45	-27844.50	-0.60

Fig 4.9: Chart that shows Total Income to Working capital ratio data of UIICL for past 6 years

Source: Annual reports of UIICL taken from uiic.co.in/public-disclosures

Interpretation:

It can be observed from the table 4.9 and figure 4.9 representing the other performance of UIICL besides profitability, liquidity and solvency before and after covid are as follows:

The average total income to working capital ratio in pre-covid period from FY 2016-17 to 2018-19 was -0.75 times whereas the average total income to working capital ratio from FY 2019-20 to 2022-23 was -0.60 times.

It implies that Total income to Working capital ratio of UIICL has been improved from -0.75 times to -0.60 times after Covid.

ii) Total Income to Borrowings Ratio:

$$\text{Total Income to Borrowings Ratio} = \frac{\text{Total Income}}{\text{Borrowing}}$$

Table 4.11: Total Income to Borrowings Ratio

Pre-Covid				Post-Covid			
FY	Total Income	Borrowings	Ratio	FY	Total Income	Borrowings	Ratio
2016-17	15455.98	4.99	3095.03	2019-20	16534.95	900.00	18.37
2017-18	15475.24	900.00	17.19	2020-21	16244.90	900.00	18.05
2018-19	16678.77	900.00	18.53	2022-23	17009.50	900.00	18.90
Total	47609.99	1804.99		Total	49789.35	2700.00	
Average	15870.00	601.66	26.38	Average	16596.45	900.00	18.44

Fig 4.11: Chart that shows Total Income to Borrowings ratio data of UIICL for past 6 years

Source: Annual reports of UIICL taken from uiic.co.in/public-disclosures

Interpretation:

It can be found from the table 4.11 and figure 4.11 representing the other performance of UIICL besides profitability, liquidity and solvency before and after covid are as follows:

The average total income to borrowings ratio in pre-covid period from FY 2016-17 to 2018-19 was 26.38 times whereas the average total income to borrowings ratio from FY 2019-20 to 2022-23 was 18.44 times.

It shows that Total income to borrowings ratio of UIICL has been decreased from 26.38 times to 18.44 times after Covid.

The analysis of financial statements is, thus an important aid to financial analysis. Users of financial statements can get further insights about financial strengths and weaknesses of the company, if they properly

analyze information reported in these statements. The future plans of the company should be laid down in view of the company's financial strengths and weaknesses.

Ratio analysis is a widely used tool of financial analysis. Ratio is used as a benchmark for the financial position and performance of a firm. As a tool of financial management, ratios are of crucial significance. Ratio analysis is relevant in assessing the performance of a firm in respect of the following aspects: Liquidity Position, Long term Solvency, Operational Efficiency, Overall profitability, Inter firm Comparison, Financial Statement Analysis, Comparative Statement Analysis, Common size statement Analysis.

9. FINDINGS:

- It's observed that post-covid net profit ratio of United India Insurance Co. Ltd. has been decreased from -5.86% to -9.25% though there is an average increase in the income by 726 Cr during post-covid period from FY 2019-20 to 2021-22. It's due to increase in operating expenses and claim outgoes.'
- It's noticed that Operating profit ratio of UIICL has been decreased from -8.25% to -8.71% during its post-covid period. The average net loss of UIIC has been increased from Rs.1,310 crores of 3-year pre-covid period to Rs. 1,445 Crores during post 3-year covid-period.
- It's found that current liquidity ratio of UIICL has been increased slightly from 0.22 to 0.24 times after Covid. The average current assets increased from Rs.5,955 crores of 3-year pre-covid period to Rs. 8,562 Crores during post 3 year covid-period whereas the average current liabilities are increase from Rs.36,407 crores of pre-covid period to Rs. 26,992 Crores during post 3 year covid-period. The average assets were increased by 44% whereas the average liabilities were increased by 35%.
- It's observed that that absolute liquidity of UIICL has been improved from 0.07 to 0.08 times after Covid. The average cash and Bank balances were increased from Rs.1,900 Crores of 3-year pre-covid period to Rs.2,832 Crores during 3 year post-covid period.
- It's noticed that Debt Equity ratio of UIICL has been increased from 0.15 to 0.23 times after Covid. There is no much debt component in UIIC till FY 2016-17. The average Debt was increased from Rs.607 Crores of 3 year pre-covid period to Rs. 921 Crores during 3-year post-covid period. There is no much change is Equity.
- It's found that during pre-covid, the average total assets to debt ratio from FY 2016-17 to 2018-19 was 5987% whereas the average total assets to debt ratio from FY 2019-20 to 2022-23 was 4560%. It indicates that Total assets to Debt ratio of UIICL has been reduced from 5987% to 4560% after Covid. This ratio is having its highest value in FY 2016-17.
- It's identified that Fixed assets to Debt ratio of UIICL has been increased from 32.07% to 35.48% after Covid. The average fixed assets were increased from Rs.195 Crores of 3-year pre-covid period to Rs. 327 Crores during 3-year post-covid period.
- It's observed that during pre-covid, the average total income to fixed assets ratio from FY 2016-17 to 2018-19 was 8150% whereas the average total income to fixed assets ratio from FY 2019-20 to 2022-23 was 5081%.
- It's notices that total income to Working capital ratio of UIICL has been improved from -0.75 times to -0.60 times after Covid.
- It's found that the average total income to investment ratio in pre-covid period from FY 2016-17 to 2018-19 was 0.53 times whereas the average total income to investment ratio from FY 2019-20 to 2022-23 was 0.50 times.
- It's is identified that total income to borrowings ratio of UIICL has been decreased from 26.38 times to 18.44 times after Covid.
- The premium underwritten has been fluctuating for the past 6 years. The maximum income was generated in the FY 2021-22 i.e. Rs.17,009 Crores though the premium procured in that year is 15,722 Crores which is the least in the past 6 years. The maximum gross has been underwritten in FY 2019-20 i.e. Rs. 17515 Crores.
- The share of Motor Premium has been declined in the last 5 years from 41% to 35% whereas the share of Health premium during post-covid has been increased to 40% from that of pre-covid which used to be 32% in FY 2017-18. Now, the premium of health portfolio is 6,316 Crores whereas that of Motor portfolio is 5,478 Crores only. Covid has opened the new doors for the expansion of Health port-folio not only in UIICL but also in entire general insurance industry in India.
- The UIICL has shown operating loss for the past 6 years except in FY 2017-18 where there is operating profit of 543 Crores due to least claim outgoes and closure of duplicate claims in their software.
- Paid-up capital has been constant at 150 Crores till FY 2018-19 which was later increased to 200 Crores in FY 2019-20, Later increased to around 385 Crores in FY 2020-21 and Rs. 3905 Crores in FY 2021-22.

- Net worth of firm in FY 2021-22 was declined to Rs.2095 Crores from that of Rs. 3817 Crores in the FY 2016-17. The least net worth was found in FY 2019-20 with value of Rs.1443 Crores.
- The value of Total Assets of UIICL has been increased to Rs. 45,066 Crores from that of Rs.33,818 Crores in the FY 2016-17.
- Earnings per share (EPS) has been negative since FY 2016-17 except in FY 2017-18 which is Rs.66.84/-. The least of value of EPS was (-) Rs.128 was encountered in FY 2016-17.
- Book value of share has declined to its least value i.e. Rs.5.51 in the FY 2021-22 from that of Rs.254.46 in the FY 2016-17. The Book value of share reached its maximum value in the FY 2017-18 which is Rs.320/-.
- The solvency margin of UIIC has come down to 0.51 as on 31.03.2022 from 1.0 as on 31.03.2021 which was below the stipulated margin i.e. 1.5 as per IRDAI Regulations. It had maximum solvency margin of 1.54 and 1.52 respectively in FY 2017-18 and 2018-19.

10. SUGGESTIONS

• It could be suggested that more focus to be given on digitization both in the distribution channel as well as claim settlement methods. Digital underwriting can be used to maximize customer reach. They should establish risk management teams to assess and respond to the crisis. Most of digital friendly insurers have improved their market during this covid time compared to traditional PSUs

• It could be advised that the loss-making UIICL branches with less/zero profitability and higher expenses has to be closed, and some of them could be merged with the offices nearby in order to control the operating expenses.

• Few mergers and closures have been initiated with in the Vizag Regional office of UIIC are:

1. DO3 Vizag is proposed to be merged with DO1 Vizag
2. DO Srikakulam is proposed to be downgraded to Branch
3. DO2 Nellore is proposed to be merged with DO1 Nellore
4. BO Vizianagaram is proposed for closure
5. BO Parvathipuram is proposed to be downgraded as Micro Office
6. BO3 Vijayawada is proposed to be merged with DO1 Vijayawada
7. BO Gajuwaka is proposed to be downgraded as Micro Office
8. BO Tenali is proposed for closure
9. BO Kavali is proposed for closure
10. BO3 Nellore is proposed for closure

* It could be suggested for reforms through organizational restructuring and its real-time measurement, allocation of specific roles.

Organizational Restructuring:

(1) Providing an operating framework and digitally-enabled workflows to:

(a) Seamlessly converting the Operating Offices (OOs) into Customer Experience and Business Development Centers while centralising Underwriting/Claims/Accounts, etc. into the Regional Hubs.

(b) activating all three key channels for retail business growth namely, Agency, Bancassurance and Alternative channels through suitable sales management, incentives and rewards processes.

(2) Providing capacity planning framework through manpower redistribution for both Business Development (BD) and Non-BD roles, with a clear focus on retail business through preunderwritten products and simplified processes.

(3) Providing a comprehensive reskilling/up - skilling and capability building framework for BD, Non-BD, large corporate and vertical teams to cope with the above restructuring in a confident and motivated manner.

(4) Handholding the UIICL in implementing the new organization structure across functions and geographies by providing carefully designed and sensitively implemented change management approach and communication framework.

i) It could be suggested for reforms through performance management as well as performance indicators for sales, non-sales and support staff, capacity and capability building and carefully crafted change management approach.

Performance Management and Measurement:

(1) Designing objective and quantifiable KPIs for each unique role along with their measurable outcomes and its integration with the performance appraisal system for UIICL to achieve y-o-y milestones.

(2) Based on the above KPIs, creating performance dashboards for each sales and non-sales staff at the Operating Offices, Regional Offices and Head Office as well as across functions linked with the core system.

ii) It could be suggested for simplifying the claim settlement process. The payment of claims has become a challenge for the Insurers. UIICL need to carefully evaluate and simplify claims processing virtually by upgrading interactive voice-response systems. Artificial Intelligence and Robotics can replace field visits in order to reduce it's TOT (Turn around Time) in claim settlement.

iii) UIICL has started experiencing liquidity and solvency challenges. UIICL is required to closely monitor their liquidity and ensure financial resilience by maintaining prescribed regulatory solvency. It's advised to manage the investor community, intra-group stakeholders, and rating agencies on overall performance and stability.

iv) It could be suggested to improve the EPS (Earnings per share) to protect the investor's interest in the company and Book value per share by increasing assets and reducing liabilities.

v) It's advised to monitor the crisis and initiate the necessary measures to communicate and manage the employees and customers effectively. They must maintain frequent communications with regulators, customers, partners, agents, and brokers, shareholders to build confidence and ensure continuity of service and rethink processes.

vi) It could be suggested for launching of new products in lieu of traditional fire and motor policies. The UIICL has managed risks traditionally through the products sold by the intermediaries and protected against threats. UIICL should sell more products with better flexibility and convenience. They can launch innovative and more capital-efficient insurance products for specific risks. During the COVID-19 Crisis, The Insurance Regulatory and Development Authority of India (IRDAI) has made health insurance products more customer-friendly and aimed at bringing maximum people under the insurance umbrella. The Internet of Things will help the UIICL to initiate the damage repair and claim process in auto insurance. Voice Analytics can be used to analyze and record customer interaction and experiences.

vii) It could be advised for the mechanization of distribution channels. The UIICL distribution channel nationally has got affected by the Pandemic and private players. There is a need for the UIICL to rethink their distribution model and establish a digital agency channel for online recruitment, selection, and training with videos. They should encourage the sales forces and also the intermediaries to move entirely online to improve productivity. The handsome reward and recognition schemes have to be introduced for agents and intermediaries. The strategies have to be re-evaluated, including business lines and products. UIICL need to adapt to the Customers' expectations of what products and solutions they need. Channel strategies will need to be updated. New operating models viewed as unachievable will be at the forefront of planning. Investments in automation, including AI and RPA, have to be increased. The M&A opportunities for insurers may crystallize the further growth in existing lines of business or new segments.

11. CONCLUSION

We know that the United India Insurance Company Limited as a large organization might have long gestation period and it requires the sound financial system. But at present financial performance is not up to the mark. Although insurers can contribute to financial stability on account of both their capacity to reallocate risks in the economy and their often-long-term investment horizons, they also have the potential to destabilize the financial system of United India Insurance Company Limited.

REFERENCES

1. Almajali, Y. A., Alamro, A. S., & Al-Soub, Z. Y. (2012). Factors Affecting the Financial Performance of Jordanian Insurance Companies Listed at Amman Stock Exchange. *Journal of Management Research*, 4(2), 266-289.
2. Basnet, H. (2005). A comparative study on Financial Performance between the Himalayan Bank and Nabil bank. An Unpublished MBS Dissertation, Central Department of Management, T.U. Kathmandu.
3. Estrella, A., Park, S., and Peristiani, S. (2000). Capital ratios as predictors of bank failure. *FRBNY Economic Policy Review*. Vol 6 , 33-52.
4. Harrington, S. E. (2009). The financial crisis, systemic risk, and the future of insurance regulation. *Journal of Risk and Insurance*, 76(4), 785-819.
5. Kumar, P. (2013). Testing of Financial Performance of Nepalese Life Insurance Companies by CAMELS Parameters. *Journal of Business and Management*, School of Business, Pokhara University, 10(4), 1-11.
6. Mehari, D., and Aemiro, T. (2013). Firm specific factors that determine insurance companies' performance in Ethiopia. *European Scientific Journal*, 9(10)
7. Mamduh, Hanafi and Abdul Halim, 2016. *Financial Statement Analysis*, Yogyakarta.
8. Rao, S. M., & Srinivasulu, R. (2013). Contribution of Insurance Sector to Growth and Development of the Indian Economy. *IOSR Journal of Business and Management (IOSR-JBM)*, 7(4), 45-52.
9. Weston, J. F. and Copeland, T E. (1992). *Managerial Finance*. New York: The Dryden Press.

10. Ward, D. and Zurbrugg, R. (2000). Does insurance promote economic growth? Evidence from OECD countries. *Journal of Risk and Insurance*, 67(4), pp. 489-506.